

Development and Implementation of an Educational Module on Situational Leadership During Intraoperative Crises

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Background

- The anesthesia provider is often tasked with assuming a leadership role during intraoperative crises
- Knowledge gaps exist among anesthesia providers involving inadequate utilization of crisis checklists, ineffective intraoperative communication, and a lack of training with situational leadership skills

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this DNP project was to effectively develop a situational leadership educational module for anesthesia providers in order to improve crisis management leadership during the perioperative period

Literature Review

- Aviation training and Crew Resource Management provide a blueprint for anesthesia providers regarding effective leadership and teamwork (Lark et al., 2018)
- Enhanced situational leadership qualities displayed by anesthesiologists leads to improved patient outcomes and positively related team performance (Wacker & Kolbe, 2014)
- Online training allows for increased accessibility and knowledge gains (Haskins et al., 2018; Serwetnyk et al., 2018)

Methods

Design:

Creation of module and evaluation from Delphi group

Sample:

Convenience sample of three anesthesia providers from Southern California

Measures:

Level of effectiveness and applicability of module using seven-point Likert scale

Intervention:

Online educational training module

Educational Module

Results

- All anesthesia providers **agreed** or **strongly agreed** that length of the educational module was appropriate and that the module effectively clarified the use of the crisis checklist and the incorporation of situational leadership skills in daily practice
- All providers **strongly agreed** that the educational module provided applicable themes and examples of leadership during intraoperative crises
- One provider felt that the **utilization of narration** would further enhance the effectiveness of the module

Discussion

- Anesthesia providers felt that the online module presented information applicable to their practice, suggesting that the e-learning format was a highly effective mode of teaching
- Responses to the module were overall favorable, demonstrating that this training module improves anesthesia providers' knowledge of situational leadership
- Further refinements to the educational module, such as the addition of narration, should be considered prior to piloting the module in the healthcare setting

Limitations

- Few studies focused specifically on leadership by anesthesia providers during intraoperative crises
- Existing scientific studies were quantitative and qualitative studies which demonstrated lower levels of evidence and bias due to non-random samples or small sample sizes
- The module included only two examples of critical events (i.e. hemorrhage and failed intubation scenarios)
- The results of the post-module survey included a small sample size

Recommendations

- Pilot the module at one or two Southern California anesthesia departments in order to evaluate situational leadership knowledge
- Further enhance the educational module from data collected from anesthesia providers after training in situational leadership during intraoperative crises
- Continued training focused on the adaption of crisis management checklists during the perioperative period
- Integrate annual situational leadership training

References

